

Speculation on Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution From a Microcanonical Power Law Part II

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In (1), a power law distribution $f(p)dp$ in p (i.e. the magnitude of momentum of the n th particle with a constant total energy E). The approach is to use the constraint $\sum e_i = E$ with $e_i = p_i^2/2m$ (nonrelativistic). This is then interpreted as n -sphere. The resulting distribution is:
 $f(p) = C (1 - p^2/RR)^{\text{power } (n-3)/2}$ where $RR/2m = EE$. This approach is identical to finding the probability distribution of a vector component, i.e. $n=2$ as shown in (2).

In Part I, we suggested that one may consider the problem in terms of $\sum e_i = E$ without using a n -sphere approach. In such a case, each e_i seems to carry the same "weight". Here we investigate this in more detail. We consider the case of $n=2$. The n -sphere approach leads to $f(p) = C(1 - p^2/RR)^{\text{power } -1/2}$. We suggest focusing on considering how many states may be created for $n-1$ particles, if the n th particle has energy e . For a two particle case, we suggest that if the second particle has energy e , the second particle can only be in one state, namely $E-e$. Thus each e should carry the same weight, or $P(e)de = de/E$ which is normalized and leads to $eave = E/2$. This differs from (1) as does the case of 3 particles.

We consider cases with more particles and see that the number of states is proportional to $(E-e)^{\text{power}(n-2)}$. For three particles, this approach also differs from (1), but it also leads to a power law which becomes a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution in the case of large n .

Two Particles as a Vector

In the case of two particles (moving in 1-dimension), the approach of (1) is to write:

$$P_1 p_1 + p_2 p_2 = RR \quad ((1))$$

If one associates p_1 with x and p_2 with y , this is like a vector magnitude equation. In (2), a two-vector is directly considered and a probability distribution found for B_x in (B_x, B_y) . This is the same result found in (1). Thus, the solution of (1) forces one to consider a vector with constant magnitude, which is consistent with ((1)). The calculation depends on stating that the probability is constant in θ i.e

$$P(\theta) d\theta = C \cdot d\theta$$

Then $B \cos(\theta) = B_x$ so $dB_x = B |\sin(\theta)| d\theta$. Thus:

$$d\theta = dB_x / \{B |\sin(\theta)|\} \text{ with } \sin(\theta) = B_x/B.$$

In other words, B_x is not uniformly distributed on the x axis in the vector approach. The vector approach treats tiny arc lengths, i.e. Radius $d\theta$ as the equally spaced units. This is fine for a vector, but 2 particles moving in one dimension do not constitute a vector, we argue, even though ((1)) holds.

In Part I, however, we asked whether one may consider this problem by only using e and not $pp/2m$. We suggested that each e (after perhaps removing a couple of particles, the last and the first), should give a power law for weights. We intend to consider this in more detail here, but first we consider the general result from (1):

$$f(p) dp = dp C (1 - pp/RR)^{\text{power}((n-3)/2)} \quad ((2))$$

For $n=1$, one obtains a distribution when one should not. For $n=2$, one obtains:

$$f(p)dp C dp \sqrt{1-pp/RR} \quad ((3))$$

((3)) may be used to show that the average energy is: $.5 RR/2m$ which is what is expected.

For $n=3$, one has $f(p)dp = \text{constant}$.

Thinking in Terms of Energy Only

We reconsider the problem in terms of e only, without vector considerations. We first consider some simple examples. Imagine one has two particles with a total energy of 4, with energy only existing in increments of 1. Then:

If particle 1 has energy 4 -particle 2 has energy 0 etc

One may immediately see that for any given energy for particle 1, one has only one state for particle 2. Thus, unlike (1) i.e. ((3)), we suggest that:

$$\text{For two particles, probability is constant i.e. } P(e)de = de/E \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is normalized and also leads to $e_{ave} = E/2$.

For 3 particles and total energy of 4, one has:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Particle 1 has energy 4} &\rightarrow (\text{particle 2, particle 3}) = (0,0) \\ \text{Particle 1 has energy 3} &\rightarrow (\text{particle 2, particle 3}) = \{ (0,1), (1,) \} \\ \text{Particle 1 has energy 2} &\rightarrow (\text{particle 2, particle 3}) = \{ (1,1), (2,0), (0,2) \} \quad ((5)) \end{aligned}$$

One may see from ((5)) that $P(e)de$ is not a constant as suggested by ((3)).

We suggest that if a particle may exist in an energy range E_1 , then the number of states it may have is proportional to E_1 . This is then the unnormalized weight associated with an energy range. We use this to consider a number of cases.

$n=2$ particle 1 has energy e , particle 2 has energy $E-e$, there is no energy range ((6))
Thus, all e have the same probability i.e. $P(e)de = de/E$.

n=3 particle 1 has energy e, particle 2 may have energy from 0 to E-e

Thus, $P(e)de$ proportional to $(E-e) = (E-e)$ power $(n-2)$. ((7))

n=4 particle 1 has energy e, The number of states for the other 2 particles (the third is automatically given) is:

$\int_0^{E-e} de_3 \int_0^{E-e-e_3} de_2 = .5 (E-e)$ power $(2) = C (E-e)$ power $(n-2)$ ((8))

n=5 particle 1 has energy e. The number of states for the other 3 particles (the 4th has a given energy) is proportional to:

$\int_0^{E-e} de_3 \int_0^{E-e-e_3} de_2 \int_0^{E-e-e_3-e_2} de_4$

This integrates to: $\frac{1}{6} (E-e)$ power $(3) = \frac{1}{6} (E-e)$ power $(n-2)$.

A pattern appears to emerge. Thus we suggest that the power law at work is related to:

$P(e)de$ proportional to $C (E-e)$ power $(n-2) de$ ((9))

This differs from the result of (1). $e=pp/2m$. If one uses $(E-e) = p_1p_1/2m$, then $-de = p_1/m dp_1$ and one may write ((9)) in terms of dp_1 .

In the high n limit one obtained $\exp(-e/E)$. This is related to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, but is not quite the distribution because $E=.5T$ for a one dimensional particle and one has $\exp(-e/E)$ and not $\exp(-e/T)$. If the factor $(E-e)$ is replaced by $\sqrt{E-e}$ then one obtains the exact Maxwell-Boltzmann result with $E=.5T$. If one uses the form $\exp(-e/Parameter)$ then this may be normalized and the parameter linked to average energy. Then, the parameter becomes T.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we examine the results of (1) more closely in terms of energy alone (no vectors) and find different values for n=2, n=3. Higher n values do follow a very similar power law, except that we have the factor $(E-e)$ instead of $\sqrt{E-e}$. In the high n limit, we also obtain a Maxwell-Boltzmann form.

References

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